

HCR's Rank Formula II: Rank of Selective Linear Permutations

Harish Chandra Rajpoot

M.M.M. University of Technology, Gorakhpur-273010 (UP), India

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1. Introduction

The linear permutations of digits and alphabetic symbols constitute a fundamental topic in combinatorics and discrete mathematics, with well-established methods for counting and ordering arrangements of elements in a sequence [1]. Classical treatments of permutations and combinations provide systematic procedures for determining the number of possible arrangements and for organizing them according to lexicographic or numerical order [2]. However, comparatively less emphasis has been placed on permutations involving non-algebraic objects possessing distinguishable physical attributes such as shape, size, colour, or surface pattern. In practice, such objects can be represented symbolically, enabling their permutations to be analysed within the framework of standard combinatorial techniques [1,3]. Although the enumeration of linear permutations is straightforward through factorial-based formulas and their generalizations, determining the precise hierarchical position (or rank) of a specific permutation within an ordered list remains a more intricate problem. For instance, numbers obtained by permuting digits may be arranged in increasing or decreasing numerical order, while words can be systematically organized in lexicographic sequence according to dictionary conventions [2]. Consequently, methods for ranking and un-ranking linear permutations are of both theoretical and practical significance in combinatorics, computer science, and information processing. The hierarchical position (or rank) of a specific permutation in a set of all permutations of given articles (algebraic or non-algebraic) can be easily determined using HCR's Rank Formula-I but this method is not applicable when the repetition of articles is permitted in the permutations [4,5]. Motivated by this requirement, the present work introduces HCR's Rank Formula-II, which provides a direct analytical procedure for computing the rank of any arbitrarily selected linear permutation from the complete set of permutations of a given collection of elements, including situations in which repetition of elements is permitted. The proposed formulation extends conventional ranking approaches and offers a generalized framework applicable not only to symbolic permutations but also to arrangements of physically distinguishable objects.

2. Selective Linear permutations

These are the linear permutations which are obtained by permuting certain articles when their repetition is allowed. Since these are obtained by the ways (or methods) of selecting the given articles with their replacement so called selective linear permutations. For example, total no. of 7-digit numbers formed by using 2, 5, 6 is equal to $3 \times 3 \times 3 \times 3 \times 3 \times 3 \times 3 = 3^7 = 2187$ if the repetition of the digits is allowed. We are here interested to study these selective linear permutations by finding out their ranks & arranging them according to the respective ranks.

2.1. Set of Linear Permutations: It is a group of all the possible linear permutations, each having equal no. of the articles, arranged in their hierarchical ranks (i.e. mathematically correct order of priority on the basis of pre-defined linear sequence of all the given articles).

2.2. Pre-defined Order: It is the linear sequence (arrangement) of certain articles in the correct order of priority.

A pre-defined order of given articles is always required for ranking of all the linear permutations of a set. All the linear permutations are arranged according to this pre-defined order of the given articles.

For ease of understanding, **order of priority** of articles is indicated by arrows from **left to right** on the basis of priority (any easily distinguishable property of articles) which may be increasing or decreasing or same in nature

Pre-defined linear arrangement of digits in increasing order

$0 \rightarrow 1 \rightarrow 2 \rightarrow 3 \rightarrow 4 \rightarrow 5 \rightarrow 6 \rightarrow 7 \rightarrow 8 \rightarrow 9$

Pre-defined linear arrangement of digits in decreasing order

$9 \rightarrow 8 \rightarrow 7 \rightarrow 6 \rightarrow 5 \rightarrow 4 \rightarrow 3 \rightarrow 2 \rightarrow 1 \rightarrow 0$

Pre-defined linear arrangement of letters in correct alphabetic order

$A \rightarrow B \rightarrow C \rightarrow D \dots \dots K \rightarrow L \rightarrow M \dots \dots Q \rightarrow R \rightarrow S \dots \dots W \rightarrow X \rightarrow Y \rightarrow Z$

Pre-defined linear arrangement of letters in reverse alphabetic order

$Z \rightarrow Y \rightarrow X \rightarrow W \dots \dots S \rightarrow R \rightarrow Q \dots \dots M \rightarrow L \rightarrow K \dots \dots D \rightarrow C \rightarrow B \rightarrow A$

Example 1. Digits can be arranged either in increasing or in decreasing order. This order is called pre-defined order. Consider the digits 3, 9, 5, 3, 3, 1 which are arranged in their increasing order, keeping similar ones together, as follows

$1 \rightarrow 3 \rightarrow 3 \rightarrow 3 \rightarrow 5 \rightarrow 9$

2. Alphabetic letters are arranged in their alphabetic order or reverse order. This alphabetic order is the pre-defined order for the given alphabetic letters. Consider the letters L, A, H, P, P, N, D, D which are arranged in their alphabetic order, keeping similar ones together, as follows

$A \rightarrow D \rightarrow D \rightarrow H \rightarrow L \rightarrow N \rightarrow P \rightarrow P$

3. Non-algebraic things can be arranged in any order depending on our desire or preference of their property like shape, size, colour & value etc. Thus, we can select or make any pre-defined order of such non-algebraic articles. Some linear arrangements of non-algebraic articles in their hierarchical ranks

$L \rightarrow \textcircled{R} \rightarrow \exists \rightarrow \textcircled{C} \rightarrow \varepsilon \rightarrow \beta \rightarrow \alpha$ (Having different shapes)

$\textcircled{C} \rightarrow \textcircled{C} \rightarrow \textcircled{C}$ (Having different colours)

$\exists \rightarrow M \rightarrow \Gamma \rightarrow M \rightarrow \beta \rightarrow \textcircled{R} \rightarrow \varepsilon \rightarrow \varepsilon$ (Having different shapes & colours)

2.3. Formerity (F) : *Formerity (F)* of any article in a given linear permutation is equal to the no. of the distinct articles appearance before (left side) in the pre-defined linear sequence of all the distinct articles. *Formerity (F)* of any article remains constant irrespective of its repetition (frequency) in a given linear permutation because it depends only on the pre-defined linear sequence of articles which is unique for whole the set of the linear permutations having equal no. of the articles.

2.4. Permutation Value: Permutation Value (PV) of i^{th} article from the first (left most) place in a given linear permutation having total x number of the articles, is given as

$$PV = F_i \times n^{x-i}$$

Where, i = order of place of that article from the first (left most) place in the given linear permutation

Example: Consider a 9-digit number having non-zero digits 787747443 it has four distinct digits 3, 4, 7 & 8

∴ Total no. of the distinct articles, $n = 4$

Total no. of the articles in the permutation, $x = \text{total no. of the digits in } 787747443 = 9$

These distinct digits has following **pre defined linear sequence**: $3 \rightarrow 4 \rightarrow 7^* \rightarrow 8$

Now, consider any digit say 7 which lies at 6th place from the left most place in 787747*443 (as labelled '*') hence take $i = 6$ & there are two digits 3 & 4 appearing before it in pre-defined linear sequence (as labelled '*')

∴ Formerity of labelled 7, $F(7^*) = 2$

Now, the permutation value (PV) of labelled 7 can be given as

$$PV(7^*) = F(7^*) \times n^{x-i} = 2 \times 4^{9-6} = 2 \times 4^3 = 128$$

3. HCR's Rank Formula-II

According to HCR's Rank Hypothesis, if the repetition of n no. of the distinct articles is allowed then the rank of any linear permutation, given or randomly selected from a set (group) of all the linear permutations each having x no. of the articles (repeated or non-repeated or both) & arranged in the correct order, is given by the sum of unity (1) & Permutation Values (PV's) of all x no. of the articles in that linear permutation as follows

$$R(\text{Linear permutation}) = 1 + \{F_1 \times n^{(x-1)} + F_2 \times n^{(x-2)} + F_3 \times n^{(x-3)} + \dots + F_{x-2} \times n^2 + F_{x-1} \times n^1 + F_n \times n^0\}$$

$$\Rightarrow R(\text{Linear permutation}) = 1 + \sum_{i=1}^{i=x} F_i \times n^{(x-i)}$$

Where, $F_i = \text{Formerity of } i^{\text{th}}$ article from the first (left most) place in the given linear permutation

= No. of the articles appearing before any article in pre defined linear sequence of all the articles

$n = \text{Total no. of the distinct articles taken for all the permutations in the set or}$

= Maximum no. of the distinct articles appearing in all the permutations in the set &

$x = \text{No. of the articles in the given (or randomly selected) linear permutation}$

Let there be n no. of the distinct articles (i.e. all are equally significant & having distinguishable appearances). Now if the repetition of these articles is allowed then the total no. (N_t) of the linear permutations each having x no. of the articles is given as

$N_t = \text{no. of ways of filling } x \text{ no. of the places by } n \text{ no. of the articles while repetition is allowed}$

$$= n \times n \times n \times n \dots \dots \dots \times n \times n \text{ (} x \text{ times)} = n^x$$

$$\Rightarrow N_t = n^x$$

Above result is applicable for equally significant articles in the linear permutations like for the numbers having only significant digits or non-zero digits.

Note: If there are total n no. of the distinct articles out of which n_o no. of the articles are non-significant articles (like zero-digit) which must not appear at the first (left most) place in any of the linear permutations of the set then the total no. (N_t) of the significant linear permutations each having x no. of the articles

N_t = Total no. of the linear permutations – non significant linear permutations (N_o)

Let's calculate total no. (N_o) of the significant linear permutations each having x no. of the articles, assuming that the first place of each permutation is occupied by any of the non-significant articles, as follows

$$\begin{aligned} \Rightarrow N_o &= n_o \times [\text{No. of ways of filling } (x - 1) \text{ places by } n \text{ no. of the articles (repetition allowed)}] \\ &= n_o \times [n \times n \times n \times n \dots \dots \dots \times n \times n \text{ (} (x - 1) \text{ times)}] = n_o n^{x-1} \\ &(\because \text{ first (left most) place is already occupied by the non significant articles }) \end{aligned}$$

$$\therefore N_t = n^x - n_o n^{x-1} = (n - n_o) n^{x-1}$$

$$\Rightarrow N_t = (n - n_o) n^{x-1} \quad \forall n \geq n_o$$

Above result is extremely useful for finding out the ranks of numbers having both zero & non-zero digits.

If we are to calculate the rank of any of the linear permutations in reverse order then we first calculate rank in the correct order by using HCR's Rank Formula-II & then the rank in reverse order is given as

$$\text{Rank in reverse order} = [\text{Total no. of linear permutations}] - [\text{Rank in correct order}] + 1$$

3.1. Conditions for Application of HCR's Rank Formula-II

1. All the articles are equally likely to occur at all the places in the linear permutations of a set.
2. Repetition of the articles is allowed i.e. any article can repeat or appear any times in any permutation.
3. All the linear permutations obtained are equally important, each of them having equal no. of the articles & assumed to be arranged in their correct ranks i.e. we can't remove any permutation from the set or all the linear permutations are assumed to be present in the set (group) of all the possible linear permutations obtained by certain articles.

3.2. Verification of HCR's Rank Formula-II

Although, this formula has no mathematical derivation but it can be verified by the general result obtained by it. Let there be n no. of the distinct articles $\theta_1, \theta_2, \theta_3, \theta_4, \dots \dots \dots \theta_{n-2}, \theta_{n-1}$ & θ_n these are equally significant at all the places in all the linear permutations of the set. Now if the repetition of the articles is allowed then the total no. (N_t) of the linear permutations, each having x no. of the articles, is given as

$$N_t = n^x$$

Now, let the **pre-defined linear sequence of all these distinct articles** be as follows

$$\theta_1 \rightarrow \theta_2 \rightarrow \theta_3 \rightarrow \theta_4 \rightarrow \dots \dots \dots \rightarrow \theta_{n-2} \rightarrow \theta_{n-1} \rightarrow \theta_n$$

It is clear from the above pre-defined sequence that all the linear permutation can be arranged in their ranks. Set of all these linear permutations, each having x no. of the articles, arranged in the correct ranks can be tabulated as follows

Selective Linear Permutation	Rank (order of priority)
$\theta_1 \theta_1 \theta_1 \theta_1 \theta_1 \dots \dots \dots \theta_1 \theta_1 \theta_1 \theta_1$ (x times)	1
$\theta_1 \theta_1 \theta_1 \theta_1 \theta_1 \dots \dots \dots \theta_1 \theta_1 \theta_1 \theta_2$ (x times)	2

$\theta_1\theta_1\theta_1\theta_1\theta_1 \dots \dots \theta_1\theta_1\theta_1\theta_3$ (x times)	3
.....
.....
$\theta_n\theta_n\theta_n\theta_n\theta_n \dots \dots \theta_n\theta_n\theta_n\theta_{n-2}$ (x times)	$n^x - 2$
$\theta_n\theta_n\theta_n\theta_n\theta_n \dots \dots \theta_n\theta_n\theta_n\theta_{n-1}$ (x times)	$n^x - 1$
$\theta_n\theta_n\theta_n\theta_n\theta_n \dots \dots \theta_n\theta_n\theta_n\theta_n$ (x times)	n^x

It is clear from table, last linear permutation in the set is $\theta_n\theta_n\theta_n\theta_n\theta_n \dots \dots \theta_n\theta_n\theta_n\theta_n$ (x times). Hence, its rank must be n^x (= total no. of the linear permutations in the set).

Formerity of any article θ_n in the permutation $\theta_n\theta_n\theta_n\theta_n\theta_n \dots \dots \theta_n\theta_n\theta_n\theta_n$ (x times)

$F(\theta_n)$ = No. of the articles appearing before θ_n in above pre defined sequence of all the articles

$F(\theta_n) = n - 1$ (\because there are $(n - 1)$ articles appearing before θ_n in pre defined sequence)

Now using HCR's Formula-II to calculate its rank by adding unity (1) & the permutation values of all the x no. of the articles in that linear permutation (taken from the above set or table) as follows

$$\begin{aligned}
 R(\theta_n\theta_n\theta_n\theta_n\theta_n \dots \dots \theta_n\theta_n\theta_n\theta_n \text{ (} x \text{ times)}) &= 1 + \sum_{i=1}^{i=x} F_i \times n^{(x-i)} \\
 &= 1 + \{(n - 1) \times n^{(x-1)} + (n - 1) \times n^{(x-2)} + \dots \dots \dots + (n - 1) \times n^{(x-x+1)} + (n - 1) \times n^{(x-x)}\} \\
 &= 1 + (n - 1)\{n^{(x-1)} + n^{(x-2)} + n^{(x-3)} \dots \dots \dots n^2 + n + 1\} \\
 &= 1 + (n - 1)\{\text{sum of } x \text{ terms of a } G.P. \text{ having } a = 1 \text{ \& } r = n\} \\
 &= 1 + (n - 1)\left\{\frac{a(r^x - 1)}{r - 1}\right\} = 1 + (n - 1)\left\{\frac{1(n^x - 1)}{n - 1}\right\} = 1 + (n^x - 1) = n^x \\
 &= N_t = \text{Total no. of the linear permutations each having } x \text{ no. of the articles}
 \end{aligned}$$

We find that both the above results are equal hence HCR's Rank Formula-II is verified.

3.3. Method to finding rank of any linear permutation when the repetition of articles is permissible

The method of finding the rank of any linear permutation with repetition of articles involve the following working steps.

Step 1: Arrange all the distinct articles (elements) in their correct linear sequence. It is called **per-defined linear sequence** of the articles.

Step 2: Find out the value of Formerity (F) & then the permutation value for each of the articles in the given or randomly selected linear permutation starting from first (left most) article up to last (right most) article in that permutation with the help of per-defined linear sequence of articles (like increasing or decreasing order of digits, alphabetic order of letters etc. are pre-defined sequences well known to all).

Step 4: Now, use Rank Formula by adding unity (1) & the permutation values (PV's) of all the articles in that linear permutation to find out its rank.

3.4. Rank of a number having zero-digit(s)

Rank of number having zero digit is calculated by using rank formula-II first by assuming zero as the significant digit & then subtracting total non-significant numbers (having first place as zero) from the rank to get the correct rank of that number. Hence it is given as

$R(\text{Number with zero digit}) = (\text{Rank assuming zero as significant digit}) - (\text{non significant numbers})$

$$R(\text{Number with zero digit}) = 1 + \sum_{i=1}^{i=x} F_i \times n^{(x-i)} - n^{x-1}$$

4. Applications of HCR's Rank Formula-II with illustrative examples

4.1. Rank of Numbers

Example 1: Let's find out the rank in increasing (\uparrow) & decreasing (\downarrow) orders of a number 63328839 randomly selected from a set of all the 8-digit numbers obtained by permuting 1, 2, 3, 4, 6, 8 & 9 while the repetition of digits is allowed.

Solution. Here, total no. of distinct digits used in all the linear permutations of the set, $n = 7$ &

No. of digits in the given number 63328839, $x = 8$ (\because all the numbers have 8 digits).

Now, let's follow the steps below

Step 1: Arrange all the distinct digits 1, 2, 3, 4, 6, 8 & 9 in **increasing order** or **pre-defined linear sequence** as follows

$$1 \rightarrow 2 \rightarrow 3 \rightarrow 4 \rightarrow 6 \rightarrow 8 \rightarrow 9$$

Step 2: Now, find out value of *Formerity* (F) & permutation value (PV) for each of eight digits in the given number 63328839 starting from the left most up to the right most digit by using the definitions of Formerity (F) & Permutation Value (PV) as follows

Formerity of first (left most, $i = 1$) digit 6 (labelled in 'red') in 63328839 i.e. $F(6)$

= No. of the digits appearing before 6 in above pre defined sequence (i.e. increasing order)

$$\Rightarrow F(6) = 4 \quad (\because \text{there are four digits appearing before 6 in above pre defined sequence})$$

Now, the permutation value (PV) of labelled digit 6 is calculated as

$$PV(6) = F(6) \times n^{x-i} = 4 \times 7^{8-1} = 4 \times 7^7 = 3294172$$

Formerity of next ($i = 2$) digit 3 (labelled in 'red') in 63328839 i.e. $F(3)$

= No. of the digits appearing before 3 in above pre defined sequence (i.e. increasing order)

$$\Rightarrow F(3) = 2 \quad (\because \text{there are two digits appearing before 3 in above pre defined sequence})$$

Now, the permutation value (PV) of labelled digit 3 is calculated as

$$PV(3) = F(3) \times n^{x-i} = 2 \times 7^{8-2} = 2 \times 7^6 = 235298$$

Formerity of next ($i = 3$) digit 3 (labelled in 'red') in 63328839 *i.e.* $F(3) = 2$ (it's constant for digit 3)

Now, the permutation value (PV) of labelled digit 3 is calculated as

$$PV(3) = F(3) \times n^{x-i} = 2 \times 7^{8-3} = 2 \times 7^5 = \mathbf{33614}$$

Formerity of next ($i = 4$) digit 2 (labelled in 'red') in 63328839 *i.e.* $F(2) = 0$

= No. of the digits appearing before 2 in above pre defined sequence (i.e. increasing order)

$$F(2) = 0 \quad (\because \text{there is no digit appearing before 2 in above pre defined sequence})$$

Now, the permutation value (PV) of labelled digit 2 is calculated as

$$PV(2) = F(2) \times n^{x-i} = 0 \times 7^{8-4} = \mathbf{0}$$

Formerity of next ($i = 5$) digit 8 (labelled in 'red') in 63328839 *i.e.* $F(8) = 5$

= No. of the digits appearing before 8 in above pre defined sequence (i.e. increasing order)

$$\Rightarrow F(8) = 5 \quad (\because \text{there are five digits appearing before 8 in above pre defined sequence})$$

Now, the permutation value (PV) of labelled digit 8 is calculated as

$$PV(8) = F(8) \times n^{x-i} = 5 \times 7^{8-5} = 5 \times 7^3 = \mathbf{1715}$$

Formerity of next ($i = 6$) digit 8 (labelled in 'red') in 63328839 *i.e.* $F(8) = 5$ (it's constant for digit 3)

Now, the permutation value (PV) of labelled digit 8 is calculated as

$$PV(8) = F(8) \times n^{x-i} = 5 \times 7^{8-6} = 5 \times 7^2 = \mathbf{245}$$

Formerity of next ($i = 7$) digit 3 (labelled in 'red') in 63328839 *i.e.* $F(3) = 2$ (it's constant for digit 3)

Now, the permutation value (PV) of labelled digit 3 is calculated as

$$PV(3) = F(3) \times n^{x-i} = 2 \times 7^{8-7} = 2 \times 7 = \mathbf{14}$$

Formerity of next (last, $i = 8$) digit 9 (labelled in 'red') in 63328839 *i.e.* $F(9) = 6$

= No. of the digits appearing before 9 in above pre defined sequence (i.e. increasing order)

$$\Rightarrow F(9) = 6 \quad (\because \text{there are six digits appearing before 9 in above pre defined sequence})$$

Now, the permutation value (PV) of labelled digit 9 is calculated as

$$PV(9) = F(9) \times n^{x-i} = 6 \times 7^{8-8} = 6 \times 1 = \mathbf{6}$$

Step 3: Now, the rank of given number 63328839 is calculated by using the HCR's Rank Hypothesis as follows

$$\begin{aligned} R(63328839) &= 1 + (\text{sum of } PV's \text{ of all the digits of } 63328839) \\ &= 1 + (PV(6) + PV(3) + PV(3) + PV(2) + PV(8) + PV(8) + PV(3) + PV(9)) \end{aligned}$$

$$= 1 + (3294172 + 235298 + 33614 + 0 + 1715 + 245 + 14 + 6) = \mathbf{3565065}$$

The above steps have been shown only for ease of understanding of the procedure followed to apply HCR's Rank Formula-II. Now, we are able to directly apply this formula without showing the steps as shown above only by using the pre-defined linear sequence of given articles.

Note: Same procedure is followed in case any number (with zero & non-zero digits), alphabetic words & all other permutations of different objects having different shape, size, colour & surface design etc.

4.2. Direct Application of HCR's Rank Formula-II

The rank of given number 63328839 is directly calculated by using the HCR's Rank Formula-II as follows

Arrange all the distinct digits 1, 2, 3, 4, 6, 8 & 9 in **increasing order** or **pre-defined linear sequence** as follows

$$\mathbf{1 \rightarrow 2 \rightarrow 3 \rightarrow 4 \rightarrow 6 \rightarrow 8 \rightarrow 9}$$

$$R(63328839) = 1 + \sum_{i=1}^{i=x} F_i \times n^{x-i} = 1 + \sum_{i=1}^{i=8} F_i \times 7^{8-i}$$

$$= 1 + \{F_1 \times 7^{(8-1)} + F_2 \times 7^{(8-2)} + F_3 \times 7^{(8-3)} + F_4 \times 7^{(8-4)} + F_5 \times 7^{(8-5)} + F_6 \times 7^{(8-6)} + F_7 \times 7^{(8-7)} + F_8 \times 7^{(8-8)}\}$$

Now, setting the values of Formerity (F) for each of the digits using above pre defined linear sequence

$$R(63328839) = 1 + \{F(6) \times 7^7 + F(3) \times 7^6 + F(3) \times 7^5 + F(2) \times 7^4 + F(8) \times 7^3 + F(8) \times 7^2 + F(3) \times 7^1 + F(9) \times 7^0\}$$

$$= 1 + \{4 \times 7^7 + 2 \times 7^6 + 2 \times 7^5 + 0 \times 7^4 + 5 \times 7^3 + 5 \times 7^2 + 2 \times 7^1 + 6 \times 7^0\}$$

$$\mathbf{R(63328839) = 1 + (3294172 + 235298 + 33614 + 0 + 1715 + 245 + 14 + 6) = 3565065}$$

It means that the number 63328839, randomly selected from the set of all $N_t = 7^8 = 5764801$ eight-digit numbers, is lying at **3565065th** place in the increasing order (\uparrow) as shown in the table below.

Upward arrow (\uparrow) \Rightarrow shows the increasing order of rank for numbers

Downward arrow (\downarrow) \Rightarrow shows the decreasing order of rank for numbers

While the rank of 63328839 in the decreasing order (\downarrow) is given as

$$\mathbf{R(63328839 \downarrow) = N_t - R(63328839 \uparrow) + 1 = 5764801 - 3565065 + 1 = 2199737}$$

All the 5764801 eight-digit numbers formed by using the digits 1, 2, 3, 4, 6, 8 & 9 with the repetition can be correctly arranged in increasing & decreasing orders according to the ranks as tabulated below

Selective Linear Permutation (8-digit number)	Rank in increasing order (\uparrow)	Rank in decreasing order (\downarrow)
11111111	1	5764801
11111112	2	5764800
11111113	3	5764799
11111114	4	5764798
11111116	5	5764797
.....
.....

28991648	1527259	4237543
28991649	1527260	4237542
28991661	1527261	4237541
.....
.....
34188994	2014093	3750709
34188996	2014094	3750708
34188998	2014095	3750707
.....
.....
63328839	3565065	2199737
63328841	3565066	2199736
63328842	3565067	2199735
.....
.....
86611238	4655608	1109194
86611239	4655609	1109193
86611241	4655610	1109192
.....
.....
99999993	5764797	5
99999994	5764798	4
99999996	5764799	3
99999998	5764800	2
99999999	5764801	1

Example 2: Let's find out the rank in increasing (\uparrow) & decreasing (\downarrow) orders of a number 7059077009 randomly selected from a set of all the 10-digit numbers obtained by permuting 0, 5, 7 & 9 while the repetition of digits is allowed.

Solution. Here, n = Total no. of the **distinct digits** for all the numbers (permutations) = 4

$$x = \text{Total no. of the digits in the given number } 7059077009 = 10$$

Here, zero is non-significant digit hence the total no. of significant 10-digit numbers obtained by permuting the distinct digits 0, 5, 7 & 9 with the repetition is given as

$$N_t = (n - n_o)n^{x-1} = (4 - 1)4^{10-1} = 3 \times 4^9 = 786432$$

While, the total non-significant 10-digit numbers (i.e. zero digit occurs at first (left most) place) obtained by the distinct digits 0, 5, 7 & 9 with the repetition is given as

$$N_o = n^{x-1} = 4^9 = 262144$$

Now, arrange all the distinct digits 0, in **increasing order** or **pre-defined linear sequence** as follows

$$0 \rightarrow 5 \rightarrow 7 \rightarrow 9$$

Now, assuming zero digit as the significant and finding out the permutation value for each of the digits with the help of above pre-defined sequence. The rank of 7059077009 in increasing order (\uparrow) using rank formula-II (following the same steps as mentioned in the above example-1) is given as

$$\Rightarrow R(7059077009) = 1 + \sum_{i=1}^{i=x} F_i \times n^{x-i} - n^{x-1} = 1 + \sum_{i=1}^{i=10} F_i \times 4^{10-i} - 4^{10-1}$$

$$= 1 + \{F_1 \times 4^{(10-1)} + F_2 \times 4^{(10-2)} + F_3 \times 4^{(10-3)} + F_4 \times 4^{(10-4)} + F_5 \times 4^{(10-5)} + F_6 \times 4^{(10-6)} + F_7 \times 4^{(10-7)} + F_8 \times 4^{(10-8)} + F_9 \times 4^{(10-9)} + F_{10} \times 4^{(10-10)}\} - 262144$$

Now, set the values of Formerity (F) for each of the digits using above pre defined linear sequence

$$R(7059077009) = \{F(7) \times 4^9 + F(0) \times 4^8 + F(5) \times 4^7 + F(9) \times 4^6 + F(0) \times 4^5 + F(7) \times 4^4 + F(7) \times 4^3 + F(0) \times 4^2 + F(0) \times 4^1 + F(9) \times 4^0\} - 262143$$

$$= \{2 \times 4^9 + 0 \times 4^8 + 1 \times 4^7 + 3 \times 4^6 + 0 \times 4^5 + 2 \times 4^4 + 2 \times 4^3 + 0 \times 4^2 + 0 \times 4^1 + 3 \times 4^0\} - 262143$$

$$R(7059077009) = (524288 + 0 + 16384 + 12288 + 0 + 512 + 128 + 0 + 0 + 3) - 262143$$

$$= 291460$$

It means that the number 7059077009, randomly selected from the set of all $N_t = 3 \times 4^9 = 786432$ ten-digit numbers, is lying at 291460th place in the increasing order (\uparrow) as shown in the table below.

While the rank of 7059077009 in the decreasing order (\downarrow) is given as

$$R(7059077009 \downarrow) = N_t - R(7059077009 \uparrow) + 1 = 786432 - 291460 + 1 = 494973$$

All 786432 ten-digit numbers formed by using the digits 0, 5, 7 & 9 with the repetition can be correctly arranged in increasing & decreasing orders according to the ranks as tabulated below

Selective Linear Permutation (10-digit number)	Rank in increasing order (\uparrow)	Rank in decreasing order (\downarrow)
5000000000	1	786432
5000000005	2	786431
5000000007	3	786430
5000000009	4	786429
5000000050	5	786428
.....
.....
5999055007	258371	528062
5999055009	258372	528061
5999055050	258373	528060
.....
.....
7059077009	291460	494973
7059077050	291461	494972
7059077055	291462	494971
.....
.....
7990955905	511346	275087
7990955907	511347	275086
7990955909	511348	275085
.....
.....
9077990099	569104	217329
9077990500	569105	217828
9077990505	569106	217327
.....
.....
9999999979	786428	5
9999999990	786429	4

999999995	786430	3
999999997	786431	2
999999999	786432	1

Thus, it is very easy to apply rank formula-II to calculate the rank of any number having zero or non-zero or both the digits.

The same procedure (as mentioned in the example-1) is used in case of any other articles like letters & all other objects with different appearances (as mentioned below).

4.3. Rank of Words

Example 3: Let's find out the alphabetic rank of a word ACADEMIA randomly selected from a set of all the words, each having eight letters, obtained by permuting A, C, D, E, I & M while the repetition (replacement) of letters is allowed.

Solution. Here, total no. of distinct letters used in all the linear permutations of the set, $n = 6$ &

No. of letters in the given word *ACADEMIA*, $x = 8$ (\because all the words have 8 letters).

Now, let's follow the steps below

Step 1: Arrange all the distinct letters in A, C, D, E, I & M **alphabetic order** or **pre-defined linear sequence** as follows

$$A \rightarrow C \rightarrow D \rightarrow E \rightarrow I \rightarrow M$$

Step 2: Now, find out value of *Formerity* (F) & permutation value (PV) for each of eight letters in the given ACADEMIA starting from the left most up to the right most letter by using the definitions of Formerity (F) & Permutation Value (PV) as follows

Formerity of first (left most, $i = 1$) letter A (labelled in 'red') in **ACADEMIA** i.e. $F(A)$

= no. of the letters appearing before A in above pre defined alphabetic order

$$\Rightarrow F(A) = 0 \quad (\because \text{there is no letter appearing before } A \text{ in above pre defined sequence})$$

Now, the permutation value (PV) of labelled letter A is calculated as

$$PV(A) = F(A) \times n^{x-i} = 0 \times 6^{8-1} = 0$$

Formerity of next ($i = 2$) letter C (labelled in 'red') in **ACADEMIA** i.e. $F(C)$

= no. of the letters appearing before C in above pre defined alphabetic order

$$\Rightarrow F(C) = 1 \quad (\because \text{there is one letter appearing before } C \text{ in above pre defined sequence})$$

Now, the permutation value (PV) of labelled letter C is calculated as

$$PV(C) = F(C) \times n^{x-i} = 1 \times 6^{8-2} = 6^6 = 46656$$

Formerity of next ($i = 3$) letter A (labelled in 'red') in **ACADEMIA** i.e. $F(A) = 0$ (it's constant for A)

Now, the permutation value (PV) of labelled letter A is calculated as

$$PV(A) = F(A) \times n^{x-i} = 0 \times 6^{8-3} = 0$$

Formerity of next ($i = 4$) letter D (labelled in 'red') in *ACADEMIA* i.e. $F(D)$

= no. of the letters appearing before **D** in above pre defined alphabetic order

$$\Rightarrow F(D) = 2 \quad (\because \text{there are two letters appearing before } D \text{ in above pre defined sequence})$$

Now, the permutation value (PV) of labelled letter D is calculated as

$$PV(D) = F(D) \times n^{x-i} = 2 \times 6^{8-4} = 2 \times 6^4 = 2592$$

Formerity of next ($i = 5$) letter E (labelled in 'red') in *ACADEMIA* i.e. $F(E)$

= no. of the letters appearing before **E** in above pre defined alphabetic order

$$\Rightarrow F(E) = 3 \quad (\because \text{there are three letters appearing before } E \text{ in above pre defined sequence})$$

Now, the permutation value (PV) of labelled letter E is calculated as

$$PV(E) = F(E) \times n^{x-i} = 3 \times 6^{8-5} = 3 \times 6^3 = 648$$

Formerity of next ($i = 6$) letter M (labelled in 'red') in *ACADEMIA* i.e. $F(M)$

= no. of the letters appearing before **M** in above pre defined alphabetic order

$$\Rightarrow F(M) = 5 \quad (\because \text{there are five letters appearing before } M \text{ in above pre defined sequence})$$

Now, the permutation value (PV) of labelled letter M is calculated as

$$PV(M) = F(M) \times n^{x-i} = 5 \times 6^{8-6} = 5 \times 6^2 = 180$$

Formerity of next ($i = 7$) letter I (labelled in 'red') in *ACADEMIA* i.e. $F(I)$

= no. of the letters appearing before **I** in above pre defined alphabetic order

$$\Rightarrow F(I) = 4 \quad (\because \text{there are four letters appearing before } I \text{ in above pre defined sequence})$$

Now, the permutation value (PV) of labelled letter 'I' is calculated as

$$PV(I) = F(I) \times n^{x-i} = 4 \times 6^{8-7} = 4 \times 6 = 24$$

Formerity of next (last, $i = 8$) letter A (labelled in 'red') in *ACADEMIA* i.e. $F(A) = 0$ (it's constant for A)

Now, the permutation value (PV) of labelled letter A is calculated as

$$PV(A) = F(A) \times n^{x-i} = 0 \times 6^{8-8} = 0$$

Step 3: Now, the rank of given word ACADEMIA is calculated by using the HCR's Rank Hypothesis as follows

$$R(ACADEMIA) = 1 + (\text{sum of } PV\text{'s of all the letters of } ACADEMIA)$$

$$= 1 + (PV(A) + PV(C) + PV(A) + PV(D) + PV(E) + PV(M) + PV(I) + PV(A))$$

$$= 1 + (0 + 46656 + 0 + 2592 + 648 + 180 + 24 + 0) = \mathbf{50101}$$

Or

Rank of the given word ACADEMIA is directly calculated by using the HCR's Rank Formula-II as follows

Arrange all the distinct letters A, C, D, E, I & M in alphabetic order or pre-defined linear sequence as follows

$$A \rightarrow C \rightarrow D \rightarrow E \rightarrow I \rightarrow M$$

$$R(ACADEMIA) = 1 + \sum_{i=1}^{i=x} F_i \times n^{x-i} = 1 + \sum_{i=1}^{i=8} F_i \times 6^{8-i}$$

$$= 1 + \{F_1 \times 6^{(8-1)} + F_2 \times 6^{(8-2)} + F_3 \times 6^{(8-3)} + F_4 \times 6^{(8-4)} + F_5 \times 6^{(8-5)} + F_6 \times 6^{(8-6)} + F_7 \times 6^{(8-7)} + F_8 \times 6^{(8-8)}\}$$

Now, set the values of Formerity (F) for each of the letters using above pre defined linear sequence

$$R(ACADEMIA) = 1 + \{F(A) \times 6^7 + F(C) \times 6^6 + F(A) \times 6^5 + F(D) \times 6^4 + F(E) \times 6^3 + F(M) \times 6^2 + F(I) \times 6^1 + F(A) \times 6^0\}$$

$$= 1 + \{0 \times 6^7 + 1 \times 6^6 + 0 \times 6^5 + 2 \times 6^4 + 3 \times 6^3 + 5 \times 6^2 + 4 \times 6^1 + 0 \times 6^0\}$$

$$R(ACADEMIA) = 1 + \{0 + 46656 + 0 + 2592 + 648 + 180 + 24 + 0\} = \mathbf{50101}$$

It means that the word ACADEMIA, randomly selected from the set of all $N_t = 6^8 = 1679616$ words each having eight letters, is lying at **50101st** place in the alphabetic order as shown in the table below.

Word (Selective Linear Permutation)	Alphabetic Rank
AAAAAAAA	1
AAAAAAAC	2
AAAAAAD	3
AAAAAAAE	4
AAAAAAAI	5
.....
.....
ACADEMEM	50100
ACADEMIA	50101
ACADEMIC	50102
.....
.....
CMMEDIAC	556562
CMMEDIAD	556563
CMMEDIAE	556564
.....
.....
IMEMMMEA	1384111
IMEMMMEC	1384112
IMEMMMED	1384113

.....
MMMMMMC	1679612
MMMMMMD	1679613
MMMMMME	1679614
MMMMMMI	1679615
MMMMMMM	1679616

Example 4: Let's find out the alphabetic rank of a word **MATHEMATICS** randomly selected from a set of all the words, each having 11 letters, obtained by permuting A, C, E, H, I, M, S & T while the repetition (replacement) of letters is permissible.

Solution: Here, $n =$ Total no. of the distinct letters for all the words in the set = 8

$$x = \text{Total no. of the letters in the given word } MATHEMATICS = 11$$

Hence the total no. of 11-letter words obtained by permuting the distinct letters with the repetition or replacement is given as

$$\Rightarrow N_t = 8^{11} = 8589934592$$

Now, arrange all the distinct letters A, C, E, H, I, M, S & T in **alphabetic order (pre-defined linear sequence)** as follows

$$A \rightarrow C \rightarrow E \rightarrow H \rightarrow I \rightarrow M \rightarrow S \rightarrow T$$

$$R(MATHEMATICS) = 1 + \sum_{i=1}^{i=11} F_i \times n^{x-i} = 1 + \sum_{i=1}^{i=11} F_i \times 8^{11-i}$$

$$= 1 + \{F_1 \times 8^{(11-1)} + F_2 \times 8^{(11-2)} + F_3 \times 8^{(11-3)} + F_4 \times 8^{(11-4)} + F_5 \times 8^{(11-5)} + F_6 \times 8^{(11-6)} + F_7 \times 8^{(11-7)} + F_8 \times 8^{(11-8)} + F_9 \times 8^{(11-9)} + F_{10} \times 8^{(11-10)} + F_{11} \times 8^{(11-11)}\}$$

$$= 1 + \{F(M) \times 8^{10} + F(A) \times 8^9 + F(T) \times 8^8 + F(H) \times 8^7 + F(E) \times 8^6 + F(M) \times 8^5 + F(A) \times 8^4 + F(T) \times 8^3 + F(I) \times 8^2 + F(C) \times 8^1 + F(S) \times 8^0\}$$

Now, set the values of Formerity (F) for each of the letters using above pre defined linear sequence

$$\Rightarrow R(MATHEMATICS)$$

$$= 1 + \{5 \times 8^{10} + 0 \times 8^9 + 7 \times 8^8 + 3 \times 8^7 + 2 \times 8^6 + 5 \times 8^5 + 0 \times 8^4 + 7 \times 8^3 + 4 \times 8^2 + 1 \times 8^1 + 6 \times 8^0\}$$

$$= 1 + 5368709120 + 0 + 117440512 + 6291456 + 524288 + 163840 + 0 + 3584 + 256 + 8 + 6$$

$$= 5493133071$$

It means that the word **MATHEMATICS**, randomly selected from the set of all $N_t = 8^{11} = 8589934592$ words each having 11 letters, is lying at **5493133071st** place in the alphabetic order as shown in the table below.

Word (Selective Linear Permutation)	Alphabetic Rank
AAAAAAAAAAAA	1
AAAAAAAAAAAC	2
AAAAAAAAAAAE	3
AAAAAAAAAAAH	4
AAAAAAAAAAAI	5
.....
.....
<i>ESCEMCATEAT</i>	2975108744
<i>ESCEMCATECA</i>	2975108745
<i>ESCEMCATECC</i>	2975108746
.....
.....
<i>HSCEMENTITE</i>	4048903995
<i>HSCEMENTITH</i>	4048903996
<i>HSCEMENTITI</i>	4048903997
.....
.....
<i>MATHEMATICM</i>	5493133070
<i>MATHEMATICS</i>	5493133071
<i>MATHEMATICT</i>	5493133072
.....
.....
<i>MTSEMCEIEST</i>	6414436704
<i>MTSEMCEIETA</i>	6414436705
<i>MTSEMCEIETC</i>	6414436706
.....
.....
<i>TTTTTTTTTTH</i>	8589934588
<i>TTTTTTTTTTI</i>	8589934589
<i>TTTTTTTTTTM</i>	8589934590
<i>TTTTTTTTTTS</i>	8589934591
<i>TTTTTTTTTTT</i>	8589934592

5. Rank of Selective Linear Permutations of non-algebraic articles

It is rather simple to arrange the numbers in increasing or decreasing order & the words in the alphabetic order but it comparatively difficult to arrange the linear permutations of non-algebraic articles (all other things except digits & letters) in the correct order. For the analysis of linear permutations of such articles, we have to pre-define a linear sequence of the given articles & replace each article by a digit or a alphabetic letter to get an equivalent number or word. Rank of this number or word is simply calculated by using HCR's Rank Formula-II (used in case of repetition) & this rank will be the rank of given linear permutation. Thus, it becomes easy to calculate the rank of linear permutations of non-algebraic articles with the help of numbers or words. Digits (there are only 10 digits to replace maximum 10 distinct articles) are used for small number of the articles in a given linear permutation but letters (there are 26 letters in English Alphabet to replace maximum 26 distinct articles) can be used for higher no. of the articles. Although, combinations of digits (i.e. 2-digit, 3-digit or multi-digit numbers) can be used to replace very large (greater than 26) no. of the distinct articles but, here we would

calculate the ranks with the help of words by replacing each of the articles by an alphabetic letter according to the pre-defined linear sequence.

Working Steps:

Step 1: Arrange all the given articles (all must be distinct because repetition is allowed) in a pre-defined linear sequence (it depends on our desire, usefulness, aesthetic quality of articles) according to the basis of priority i.e. any easily distinguishable physical property like shape, size, colour etc. among the given articles.

Step 2: Replace each of the given distinct articles by a letter in the same linear sequence as that of the articles i.e. first (left most) article by **A**, next (second) by **B**, next (third) by **C** & so on depending upon the no. of articles. Thus, we get an equivalent linear sequence of alphabetic letters & an equivalent word corresponding to each of the linear permutations of the set.

Step 3: Calculate the rank of word equivalent to a given or selected linear permutation by using rank formula-II with the help of equivalent linear sequence of alphabetic letters. This will be the rank of given linear permutation of non-algebraic articles. This procedure is applied to calculate rank of any linear permutation of non-algebraic things. It will be clear from the following examples.

5.1. Illustrative Examples

5.1.1. Linear permutations of articles having different colours

Example 5: Consider the following group of 5 distinct articles identical in shape & size but dissimilar in colour

Now, the total no. of the linear permutations, each having 5 articles, obtained by permuting the above five distinct articles with the repetition (replacement) is given as

$$N_t = 5 \times 5 \times 5 \times 5 \times 5 = 5^5 = 3125$$

So far, all above 3125 linear permutations are random i.e. all these have no order of arrangement. Hence, in order to arrange all these random linear permutations we have to predefine a linear sequence of all the distinct articles according to some aesthetic quality. It is obvious that the above articles are identical in shape & size, but each of the articles above differs from other ones in colour. Thus "**colour**" among all the articles is the most suitable **distinguishable property (basis of priority)**. According to the basis of colour & utility (like usefulness, aesthetics, significance etc.), let the **pre-defined linear sequence** be as follows

$$\text{Red} \rightarrow \text{Green} \rightarrow \text{Blue} \rightarrow \text{Yellow} \rightarrow \text{Purple}$$

Hence, we can easily find out the **first linear permutation**, having 5 articles, of the set just by repeating the **first article** Red at all the 5 places as follows: $\text{RedRedRedRedRed} \Rightarrow \text{Rank is 1}$

Similarly, we can find out the **last linear permutation**, having 5 articles, of the set just by repeating the **last article** Purple at all the 5 places as follows: $\text{PurplePurplePurplePurplePurple} \Rightarrow \text{Rank is 3125}$

While, all other linear permutations, each having 5 articles, will lie between above two linear permutations

Now, randomly consider any linear permutation from the set to calculate its rank. Let it be as follows

Replace all the articles of the pre-defined sequence by alphabetic letters A, B, C, D & E respectively, we get an equivalent linear sequence as follows

$$\begin{aligned} \exists &\equiv A, & \exists &\equiv B, & \exists &\equiv C, & \exists &\equiv D \text{ \& } \exists &\equiv E \\ \Rightarrow \exists \rightarrow \exists \rightarrow \exists \rightarrow \exists \rightarrow \exists &\equiv A \rightarrow B \rightarrow C \rightarrow D \rightarrow E \end{aligned}$$

& given linear permutation, $\exists\exists\exists\exists\exists\exists\exists\exists\exists \equiv DEACBECAC$

Here, $n =$ total no. of the distinct articles $= 5$

$x =$ Total no. of articles in any permutation of the set $= 9$

Now, using HCR's Rank Formula-II, the rank of equivalent linear permutation $DEACBECAC$ in the set of all the permutations, each having 9 letters (articles) is calculated as follows

$$\begin{aligned} R(DEACBECAC) &= 1 + \sum_{i=1}^{i=9} F_i \times n^{x-i} = 1 + \sum_{i=1}^{i=9} F_i \times 5^{9-i} \\ &= 1 + \{F_1 \times 5^{(9-1)} + F_2 \times 5^{(9-2)} + F_3 \times 5^{(9-3)} + F_4 \times 5^{(9-4)} + F_5 \times 5^{(9-5)} + F_6 \times 5^{(9-6)} + F_7 \times 5^{(9-7)} + \\ &F_8 \times 5^{(9-8)} + F_9 \times 5^{(9-9)}\} \\ &= 1 + \{F(D) \times 5^8 + F(E) \times 5^7 + F(A) \times 5^6 + F(C) \times 5^5 + F(B) \times 5^4 + F(E) \times 5^3 + F(C) \times 5^2 \\ &+ F(A) \times 5^1 + F(C) \times 5^0\} \end{aligned}$$

Now, set the values of *Formerity* (F) for each of the letters using above linear sequence of letters

$$\begin{aligned} \Rightarrow R(DEACBECAC) &= 1 + \{3 \times 5^8 + 4 \times 5^7 + 0 \times 5^6 + 2 \times 5^5 + 1 \times 5^4 + 4 \times 5^3 + 2 \times 5^2 + 0 \times 5^1 + 2 \times 5^0\} \\ &= 1 + 1171875 + 312500 + 0 + 6250 + 625 + 500 + 50 + 0 + 2 = 1491803 \\ &= \text{Rank of } \exists\exists\exists\exists\exists\exists\exists\exists\exists \end{aligned}$$

It means that the linear permutation $\exists\exists\exists\exists\exists\exists\exists\exists\exists$ randomly selected from the set of all $N_t = 5^9 = 1953125$ linear permutations, each having 9 articles, is lying at **1491803rd** place in the correct order of priority as shown in the table below.

Equivalent Alphabetic Word	Linear Permutation of articles	Rank of priority
AAAAAAAAA	$\exists\exists\exists\exists\exists\exists\exists\exists\exists$	1
AAAAAAAAAB	$\exists\exists\exists\exists\exists\exists\exists\exists\exists$	2
AAAAAAAAAC	$\exists\exists\exists\exists\exists\exists\exists\exists\exists$	3
AAAAAAAAAD	$\exists\exists\exists\exists\exists\exists\exists\exists\exists$	4
AAAAAAAAAE	$\exists\exists\exists\exists\exists\exists\exists\exists\exists$	5
.....
.....
BEDCBECAB	$\exists\exists\exists\exists\exists\exists\exists\exists\exists$	757427
BEDCBECAC	$\exists\exists\exists\exists\exists\exists\exists\exists\exists$	757428
BEDCBECAD	$\exists\exists\exists\exists\exists\exists\exists\exists\exists$	757429
.....
.....

CDCEBADAE	33333333	1060080
CDCEBADBA	33333333	1060081
CDCEBADBB	33333333	1060082
.....
.....
DEACBECAB	33333333	1491802
DEACBECAC	33333333	1491803
DEACBECAD	33333333	1491804
.....
.....
EEEEEEEA	33333333	1953121
EEEEEEEB	33333333	1953122
EEEEEEEC	33333333	1953123
EEEEEEED	33333333	1953124
EEEEEEEE	33333333	1953125

5.1.2. Linear permutations of articles having different shapes and colours

Example 6: Consider the following group of 6 distinct articles dissimilar in shape, size & colour

$$\exists \theta \beta : \epsilon \forall$$

Now, the total no. of the linear permutations, each having 8 articles, obtained by permuting the above six distinct articles with the repetition (replacement) is given as

$$N_t = 6 \times 6 = 6^8 = 1679616$$

So far, all above 1679616 linear permutations are random i.e. all these have no order of arrangement. Hence, in order to arrange all these random linear permutations we have to predefine a linear sequence of all the distinct articles according to some aesthetic quality. The **distinguishable property (basis of priority)** may be taken as the **shape, size or colour** whichever is suitable to us. According to the basis of shape & utility (like usefulness, aesthetics, significance etc.), let the **pre-defined linear sequence** be as follows

$$: \rightarrow \forall \rightarrow \exists \rightarrow \epsilon \rightarrow \beta \rightarrow \theta$$

Now, replace each of the articles of above linear sequence by an alphabetic letter in the same order thus, thus we get an equivalent linear sequence of letters to calculate rank of any permutation

$$: \equiv A, \quad \forall \equiv B, \quad \exists \equiv C, \quad \epsilon \equiv D, \quad \beta \equiv E \quad \& \quad \theta \equiv F$$

$$\Rightarrow : \rightarrow \forall \rightarrow \exists \rightarrow \epsilon \rightarrow \beta \rightarrow \theta \equiv A \rightarrow B \rightarrow C \rightarrow D \rightarrow E \rightarrow F$$

Now, by using HCR's Rank Formula-II & above alphabetic sequence, rank of any of 1679616 linear permutations of the set can easily be calculated & all these are arranged in the correct ranks as tabulated

Equivalent Alphabetic Word	Linear Permutation of articles	Rank of priority
-----------------------------------	---------------------------------------	-------------------------

AAAAAAA	1
AAAAAAB¥	2
AAAAAAC∃	3
AAAAAAD£	4
AAAAAAEβ	5
.....
.....
BDEFFCAD	¥£βθθ∃:£	458644
BDEFFCAE	¥£βθθ∃:β	458645
BDEFFCAF	¥£βθθ∃:θ	458646
.....
.....
CBEEFADF	∃¥ββθ:£θ	643920
CBEEFAEA	∃¥ββθ:β:	643921
CBEEFAEB	∃¥ββθ:β¥	643922
.....
.....
DFABDCBC	£θ:¥£∃¥∃	1075113
DFABDCBD	£θ:¥£∃¥£	1075114
DFABDCBE	£θ:¥£∃¥β	1075115
.....
.....
EDFDCBAC	β£θ£∃¥:∃	1302951
EDFDCBAD	β£θ£∃¥:£	1302952
EDFDCBAE	β£θ£∃¥:β	1302953
.....
.....
FFFFFFFB	θθθθθθθ¥	1679612
FFFFFFFC	θθθθθθθ∃	1679613
FFFFFFFD	θθθθθθθ£	1679614
FFFFFFFE	θθθθθθθβ	1679615
FFFFFFF	θθθθθθθθ	1679616

Conclusion

In this paper, a new formula i.e. HCR's Rank formula-II has been introduced and applied to calculate the hierarchical rank (position) of any linear permutation when the repetition of the articles (like digits, letters & all other objects having different shape, size, colour and other distinguishable aesthetic quality) is permitted.

Note: Above articles had been derived & illustrated by Mr H.C. Rajpoot (B Tech, Mechanical Engineering)

M.M.M. University of Technology, Gorakhpur-273010 (UP) India

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Email:rajpootherishchandra@gmail.com , Author's Home Page: <https://notionpress.com/author/HarishChandraRajpoot>

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